

Report on the fourth Delphi study results

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 101120390.

Report on the fourth Delphi study “Sustainable and responsible innovation supported by academia to business collaboration”

1. Expertise structure:

- Fourteen participants are managers (R&D, innovation, CEO, incubator centre, country),
- Three entrepreneurs (including one start-up founder),
- Three innovation specialists (national technical inspector, machine learning expert, and innovation researcher at CTP)

2. Gender:

- This Delphi study had the same number of male and female participants, 10 of each gender.

First round of Delphi study results

After receiving the answers given by the respondents, their summarization follows, first at the level of each country, and then at the project level (the coordinators of each partner send summary answers to the questions to the project coordinator, and the coordinator summarizes them at the project level). The summary answers are the basis for creating a questionnaire for experts for the second round of research.

Coordinators by country deliver precisely defined statistics for each of the questions, namely:

1. Percentage of answers for YES/NO questions,
2. Summarized list (3 answers per expert, but in the final list included at least five answers with the highest frequency of appearances) to obtain a base for quantitative analysis in the next step.

1. All participants were able to define the innovation ecosystem, but some of them (20%) mentioned that they have not actually implemented theoretically suggested innovation tools such as: idea generation techniques, design production, prototyping tools, or others. They all confirmed the importance of academia-to-business (A2B) collaboration, but 85% percent of them could precisely define it. Also, not all of them were familiar with the terms sustainable and responsible innovations. Still, this was the minority of the participants (10%) so the group is considered competent to discuss the topics involved.

2. The most frequent answers concerning other research questions are presented in following table.

Table 1: Delphi study – answers systematized based on first round of interviews

Research objective (RO)	Questions
RO1	1. Can you define innovation ecosystem? *

100% Yes	
RO1	<p>1a. How would you define main characteristics of innovation ecosystem (specify at least three characteristics)?</p> <p style="text-align: center;"> flexibility and adaptability collaboration and knowledge sharing innovation culture and supportive policy creativity and multidisciplinary global connectivity cooperation among stakeholders systematic financial support </p>
RO1	<p>2. How would you define key actors of innovation ecosystem (specify at least three actors-stakeholders)?</p> <p style="text-align: center;"> start-ups investors academia government accelerators R&D centers entrepreneurs NGOs industry leaders innovative companies </p>
RO2	<p>3. What phases should be part of innovation process management, such as developing the concept, producing design, testing, piloting prototyping launching, or others (specify at least three concrete phases)?</p> <p style="text-align: center;"> opportunity identification market research idea generation and evaluation concept development prototyping testing launching feedback analysis </p>
RO2	<p>4. Have you implemented some innovation tools such as: idea generation techniques, design production, prototyping tool, or others? *</p> <p style="text-align: center;">80% Yes, 20% No</p>

<p>RO2</p>	<p>4a. What innovation tools do you find useful in business practice (specify at least three concrete tools)?</p> <p style="text-align: center;"> design thinking business model canvas rapid prototyping 3D printing brainstorming market research MVP testing simulations collaboration platforms like Trello, Asana, and Google Drive </p>
<p>RO3</p>	<p>5. How would you define sustainable innovations (specify at least three characteristics)?</p> <p style="text-align: center;"> resource efficiency and renewable resources minimal waste and circular economy environmental responsibility and social impact adaptability green technologies and emission reduction positive economic impact </p>
<p>RO3</p>	<p>6. Can you define responsible innovations? *</p> <p style="text-align: center;">90% Yes, 10% No</p>
<p>RO3</p>	<p>6a. How would you define responsible innovations (specify at least three characteristics)?</p> <p style="text-align: center;"> ethical principles transparency and inclusiveness social accountability long-term societal benefits community engagement minimizing negative impacts </p>
<p>RO3</p>	<p>7. What are key challenges of sustainable and responsible innovation in developing transitional economies (specify at least three)?</p> <p style="text-align: center;"> lack of infrastructure lack of financing lack of public awareness regulatory barriers and complex regulations limited resources weak global market connections lack of entrepreneurial culture </p>
<p>RO4</p>	<p>8. Can you define academia-to-business (A2B) collaboration? *</p> <p style="text-align: center;">85% Yes, 15% No</p>

RO4	8a. How would you define A2B collaboration? (specify at least three aspects)? joint research projects knowledge transfer and shared education student internships skill improvement leveraging research capacities market connections technological solutions innovative programs
RO4	9. Specify the key actors in A2B collaboration (at least three). universities companies innovation hubs accelerators policymakers NGOs
RO4	10. Identify the building elements necessary for establishing and advancing A2B collaborative models (at least three). clear strategy intellectual property management transparency educational programs innovation culture research incubators long-term vision
RO5	11. Which factors influence A2B collaboration for sustainable and responsible innovation (specify at least three)? legal regulations social impact innovation capacity trust government incentives education transparent communication infrastructure

RO5	<p>12. What indicators should be used to assess the impact of university-linked incubators, accelerators, and research centers in terms of innovation process management (specify at least three)?</p> <p style="text-align: center;"> number of start-ups attracted investments jobs created number of innovations financial KPIs market readiness start-up revenues number of new business models </p>
RO3	<p>13. Which societal and environmental challenges sustainable and responsible innovation usually tackle in your country (specify at least three)?</p> <p style="text-align: center;"> pollution control, waste reduction, and recycling energy efficiency and renewable energy sustainable agriculture and biodiversity conservation social inclusion and ethical practices public transport improvement and emission reduction climate action education for sustainability </p>

Source: Authors' presentation

Second round of Delphi study results

Based on the analysis of qualitative data obtained in the first round of empirical research, i.e. through in-depth interviews, but also on the basis of a previously prepared systematic literature review, an instrument is developed for the second round of research in the form of a questionnaire. The questionnaire was distributed to the same experts involved in the first round of the Delphi study to reach agreement on the key challenges of innovation process management, with special focus on responsible innovation and A2B cooperation.

For each question that involves enumerating the answers, the experts declare themselves with grades from 1 to 5, using a Likert scale, whereby the experts are given an explanation of the grades according to the following meaning of the grade:

- 1 – Completely insignificant,
- 2 – Insignificant,
- 3 – Partially significant,
- 4 – Significantly,
- 5 – Very significant.

Table 2: Questionnaire for experts

Question	Answers
----------	---------

1. How significant are the following characteristics for a successful innovation ecosystem?	1 - Completely insignificant	2 - Insignificant	3 - Partially significant	4 - Significant	5 - Very significant
a) flexibility and adaptability	1	2	3	4	5
b) collaboration and knowledge sharing	1	2	3	4	5
c) supportive policy and innovation culture	1	2	3	4	5
d) creativity and multidisciplinary approach	1	2	3	4	5
e) global connectivity	1	2	3	4	5
f) cooperation among stakeholders	1	2	3	4	5
g) systematic financial support	1	2	3	4	5
2. What are the key actors of an innovation ecosystem?	1 - Completely insignificant	2 - Insignificant	3 - Partially significant	4 - Significant	5 - Very significant
a) start-ups	1	2	3	4	5
b) investors	1	2	3	4	5
c) academia	1	2	3	4	5
d) government	1	2	3	4	5
e) accelerators	1	2	3	4	5
f) R&D centers	1	2	3	4	5
g) entrepreneurs	1	2	3	4	5
h) NGOs	1	2	3	4	5
i) industry leaders	1	2	3	4	5
j) innovative companies	1	2	3	4	5
3. How significant are the following phases in innovation process management?	1 - Completely insignificant	2 - Insignificant	3 - Partially significant	4 - Significant	5 - Very significant
a) opportunity identification	1	2	3	4	5
b) market research	1	2	3	4	5
c) idea generation and evaluation	1	2	3	4	5
d) concept development	1	2	3	4	5
e) prototyping	1	2	3	4	5
f) testing	1	2	3	4	5
g) launching	1	2	3	4	5
h) feedback analysis	1	2	3	4	5
4. How significant are the following innovation tools in business practice?	1 - Completely insignificant	2 - Insignificant	3 - Partially significant	4 - Significant	5 - Very significant
a) design thinking	1	2	3	4	5
b) business model canvas	1	2	3	4	5
c) rapid prototyping	1	2	3	4	5

d) 3D printing	1	2	3	4	5
e) brainstorming	1	2	3	4	5
f) market research	1	2	3	4	5
g) MVP testing	1	2	3	4	5
h) simulations	1	2	3	4	5
i) collaboration platforms like Trello, Asana, and Google Drive	1	2	3	4	5
5. How significant are the following characteristics of sustainable innovation?	1 - Completely insignificant	2 - Insignificant	3 - Partially significant	4 - Significant	5 - Very significant
a) resource efficiency and renewable resources	1	2	3	4	5
b) minimal waste and circular economy	1	2	3	4	5
c) environmental responsibility and social impact	1	2	3	4	5
d) adaptability	1	2	3	4	5
e) green technologies and emission reduction	1	2	3	4	5
f) positive economic impact	1	2	3	4	5
6. How significant are the following characteristics of responsible innovation?	1 - Completely insignificant	2 - Insignificant	3 - Partially significant	4 - Significant	5 - Very significant
a) ethical principles	1	2	3	4	5
b) transparency and inclusiveness	1	2	3	4	5
c) social accountability	1	2	3	4	5
d) long-term societal benefits	1	2	3	4	5
e) community engagement	1	2	3	4	5
f) minimizing negative impacts	1	2	3	4	5
7. What are the main challenges of sustainable and responsible innovation in your country?	1 - Completely insignificant	2 - Insignificant	3 - Partially significant	4 - Significant	5 - Very significant
a) lack of infrastructure	1	2	3	4	5
b) lack of financing	1	2	3	4	5
c) lack of public awareness	1	2	3	4	5
d) regulatory barriers and complex regulations	1	2	3	4	5
e) limited resources	1	2	3	4	5
f) weak global market connections	1	2	3	4	5
g) lack of entrepreneurial culture	1	2	3	4	5
8. How significant are the following aspects of A2B collaboration?	1 - Completely insignificant	2 - Insignificant	3 - Partially significant	4 - Significant	5 - Very significant

a) joint research projects	1	2	3	4	5
b) knowledge transfer and shared education	1	2	3	4	5
c) student internships	1	2	3	4	5
d) skill improvement	1	2	3	4	5
e) leveraging research capacities	1	2	3	4	5
f) market connections	1	2	3	4	5
g) technological solutions	1	2	3	4	5
h) innovative programs	1	2	3	4	5
9. What are the key actors in A2E1 - Completely insignificant	1 - Completely insignificant	2 - Insignificant	3 - Partially significant	4 - Significant	5 - Very significant
a) universities	1	2	3	4	5
b) companies	1	2	3	4	5
c) innovation hubs	1	2	3	4	5
d) accelerators	1	2	3	4	5
e) policymakers	1	2	3	4	5
f) NGOs	1	2	3	4	5
10. How significant are the following elements for establishing and advancing A2E collaborative models?	1 - Completely insignificant	2 - Insignificant	3 - Partially significant	4 - Significant	5 - Very significant
a) clear strategy	1	2	3	4	5
b) intellectual property management	1	2	3	4	5
c) transparency	1	2	3	4	5
d) educational programs	1	2	3	4	5
e) innovation culture	1	2	3	4	5
f) research incubators	1	2	3	4	5
g) long-term vision	1	2	3	4	5
11. To what extent do the following factors influence A2E collaboration for sustainable and responsible innovation?	1 - Completely insignificant	2 - Insignificant	3 - Partially significant	4 - Significant	5 - Very significant
a) legal regulations	1	2	3	4	5
b) social impact	1	2	3	4	5
c) innovation capacity	1	2	3	4	5
d) trust	1	2	3	4	5
e) government incentives	1	2	3	4	5
f) education	1	2	3	4	5
g) transparent communication	1	2	3	4	5
h) infrastructure	1	2	3	4	5
12. How significant are the following indicators for	1 - Completely insignificant	2 - Insignificant	3 - Partially significant	4 - Significant	5 - Very significant

assessing the impact of university-linked incubators, accelerators, and research centers in terms of innovation process management?					
a) number of start-ups	1	2	3	4	5
b) attracted investments	1	2	3	4	5
c) jobs created	1	2	3	4	5
d) number of innovations	1	2	3	4	5
e) financial KPIs	1	2	3	4	5
f) market readiness	1	2	3	4	5
g) start-up revenues	1	2	3	4	5
h) number of new business models	1	2	3	4	5
13. How significant are the following societal and environmental challenges that sustainable and responsible innovation usually tackles in your country?	1 - Completely insignificant	2 - Insignificant	3 - Partially significant	4 - Significant	5 - Very significant
a) pollution control, waste reduction, and recycling	1	2	3	4	5
b) energy efficiency and renewable energy	1	2	3	4	5
c) sustainable agriculture and biodiversity conservation	1	2	3	4	5
d) social inclusion and ethical practices	1	2	3	4	5
e) public transport improvement and emission reduction	1	2	3	4	5
f) climate action	1	2	3	4	5
g) education for sustainability	1	2	3	4	5

Source: Authors' presentation

USE IPM

The data collected in the second round are statistically processed. If more than 70% of the experts rated the offered answer as significant or very significant, it is considered that a consensus has been reached. The calculation is presented in previous table.

Then, the options that have more than 70% qualify to be included in the quantitative questionnaire. This Questionnaire is the basis of empirical research on a sample of at least 100 units (in all 4 countries), in order to identify the needs of organizations in these countries when it comes to technology transfer and intellectual property rights.